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Practices and Challenges of Utilization of Play Materials: In Private, Faith Based and Government Owned Preschool in Bahir Dar City

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***Abstract:** Play materials enhance the teaching/learning process by exhibiting information necessary to acquire knowledge and skills.*

In this study, availability of play material, challenges that face on teachers in using play materials and play material utilization is the main focus in order to determine their effects on the performance of the students. Play materials are tools develop or acquired to assist or facilitate teachers in transmitting, organized knowledge skills and attitudes to the learners in the preschools. Teachers use different play materials to motivate children's learning. The central problem of this study is that despite the availability of play equipment in promoting children's participation in outdoor play activities and holistic development, providing these play equipment have been ignored overtime. Challenges that lead to unutilized the provision of play equipment have not been adequately investigated and well understood, hence hindering the participation of children in outdoor play activities and eventual holistic development which could only be achieved through play with opportunity to manipulate a variety of play equipment. To this end, the purpose of this study was to identify the extent of availability of play materials for children learning in the selected preschool. To examine the extent to which teachers are properly using play materials as a teaching strategy in the elected preschool and to find out the challenges that face in utilizing play materials. The study sampled three preschools using purposive sampling technique. The research design used in the study was exploratory research design, and thematic data analysis methods were used for data analysis techniques. Data were gathered through an interview and observation checklist. Fifteen teachers and three principals were participated in the study. The data obtained through interview and observation checklist were analyzed through narration. The study findings showed that low availability of outdoor and indoor play equipment for children's holistic development. Poor indoor and outdoor organization, frequent repair and replacement of broken play equipment were also lacking. Inadequate playground

space and poor maintenance of outdoor play equipment, inadequate classroom, lack of rest room, and feeding rooms. Based on these findings it is recommended that preschool teachers should supervise children during play to ensure that the play equipment they use are safe, age appropriate and adequate. If possible teachers should improvise play equipment in cases where the school is unable to install or buy commercial play equipment as a way of improving participation by children in outdoor play activities. Preschool teachers should be serviced in the use of play equipment in outdoor play activities.

CHAPTER ONE

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

This chapter comprises of background of the study, statement of the problem, objectives, significance of the study, delimitation and limitations, operational definition of terms and organization of the study.

Agreeing to Lester and Russell (2008) play is both a complex and contested concept and has long been the subject of social and academic debate. The increase in structured play sessions and emergence of technology-based play has led to further confusion over the nature and meaning of play. What is clear is that play is an innate childhood instinct, that is not only enjoyable but also crucial to the processes of learning and development. It is varied and flexible and there is no right or wrong way to play; encompassing an endless range of play types, which could be active or passive, imaginative or exploratory, involve others or carried out alone. It is a process that is freely chosen, personally directed or engaged and intrinsically motivated. That is, children and young people determine and control the content and intent of their play by following their own instincts, ideas and interests, in their own way for their own reasons.

It is one of the significant components of a child's life. Youngsters can learn the basic and social skills and develop through playing. Also some components like, play materials, playground and play mate have an important role in play. Especially play materials have a positive impact on a child to learn and explore the world with a rich imagination in a joyful way (Celebi Oncu and Ozbay, 2005).

Play materials are tools that assist in rising children's motor skills such as balance, coordination, running, climbing, and jumping and which should be available to young children as part of their everyday routines. Kaplan offers a variety of active play materials including bean bags, parachutes, mats, and balls. (Kaplan, 2019).

According to Kenya Institute of Education (2003) play materials are meant to stimulate the total growth and development of a child. Therefore materials used in outdoor should cater / provide for the following areas; manipulation skills, visual, perception, motor skills, auditory perception, language development, exploration through feelings and social emotional needs. Some educational researchers at KIE assert that those children who are exposed to a variety of toys at an early stage develop higher levels of intellectual functioning than those who receive little or no stimulation and have no toys to play with. Play equipment also enhance a high degree of socialization and develop creativity as they play. Therefore play equipment provided to children for play should be those that promote socialization whereby children interact with each other in process of play. They should also be

versatile in that they offer children a variety of play opportunities which in turn leads to their holistic development.

Moreover, play materials are important for children's all round development in the preschool as well as at home. Play materials for social development, balls of different sizes, tricycles, rocking horses while the ones for emotional development include swings, slides, and pull-up ropes. In addition some play materials for cognitive development include counters, building blocks, abacus which means that a frame containing rods with small balls that slide along them. The pronoun it refers to the abacus used as a tool or toy for counting, and clay and plasticizers. While those for physical development include pull-up rope, slides, merry go round, swings, skipping ropes, play materials are not just recreational materials but are designed to help children learn to accomplish specific educational and developmental goals while employing active and pleasurable play (UBEC 2013).

At this point the researcher want to clarify the difference between educational material and instructional materials from that of play materials educational materials, as mentioned by Mbamba (1992:253), refer to "any object that designed and organized deliberately to support and used teaching and learning processes". He further listed educational materials such as laboratories, workshops, libraries and recreational spaces that serve to house instructional activities, furniture, learning and teaching materials which act as source or channel from which learners draw knowledge and acquire skill.

Whereas instructional materials: are a variety of materials in any format which influence the student's learning and the instructor's teaching. It may include real objects; models, charts, pictures, improvised or commercially produced. Some of the instructional materials for pre-primary education to be used during teaching and learning process which include; flashcards, pictures, calendars, toothbrushes, real objects, coins, fruits, balls, video, videotape, soap, musical instruments example drums, sticks, flute, whistles, papers and others. Ministry of Education and Vocational Training (MoEVT (2005).

Proper utilization of play materials enhances learning and ensures adequate participation on the part of the students. It may also help the teacher to teach a particular lesson more effectively or to solve a particular problem with ease.

Play materials when properly used, can supply concrete basis for conceptual thinking and reduce meaningless word responses of pupils making learning more permanent, have a high degree of interest for the pupils, develop a continuity of learning like in motion pictures, contributing to meaning of words and hence to vocabulary development, provide experiences not easily obtained by other materials and they contribute to the effectively, depth and variety of learning.

Regarding with practice of use of play materials most teachers do use the outdoor play but this is only when they are having a Physical Education. Basically, children must also have opportunities to play out door since outdoor has a large space with nature Gill (2007:16).

Additionally, Brown (2009) states that children spend long hours in the preschool but their time to engage in outdoor play is limited. This corroborates with findings of a study in Nigeria pertaining outdoor play for children and teachers' perceptions. This study found that children get time to play only during break time.

Moreover, a study on relationship between playground and cognitive development found that sampled school had various play materials in their playgrounds. However, these materials were not suitable for children's holistic development (Kerich & Okioma, 2015).

Today children are not given the time to play because of various reasons which include parental commitment to their professional work. Many parents leave their children with house helps who do not allow the children to play. Again due to high population growth especially in urban areas, many preschools do not have playgrounds and children are left to play in their classroom. Play equipment in some schools are not available at all. They are also expensive to buy and to improvise/ create (Mwaura, 1989).

In addition to this, some schools have facilities which are old and are poorly maintained thus making them a health hazard to the children some of the facilities like swings are not properly fixed thus exposing children to danger of falling during outdoor play. The work load in school is too much since the syllabus requires the children to cover so much. With that, the teachers do not see the need of providing children with facilities to play. Instead they spend the playtime in teaching number work and reading which they consider to be more important in equipping children to join class one (Lillian, 2010).

Globally, a study done in Australia by Davies (1997) on teacher's roles during children's outdoor play found that many teachers have similar beliefs that children must be carefully supervised, and teachers should give children freedom to choose the type of play activities they would like to engage in. Teacher's participated in Davies study perceived their roles as monitoring, supervising, and intervening in case children behavior is inappropriate or when they feel children are unsafe.

Additionally, a study has done in America by Jack & Christopher(2013) on playgrounds characteristics that attract children to play. Revealed that children like to play in spaces with the three main features, that is plenty of equipment, playgrounds with soft surfaces, and fenced play spaces. This means that playgrounds should be fully equipped to stimulate children interest to play as well as offer more opportunities for multiple games. The more the play spaces encourages active play, the higher the likelihood for children to participate in play and interact with their peers.

Another study done by Millicent (2010) on influence of play materials on preschool children's performance found that most teachers put more emphasis on equipping the indoor environment with play materials as opposed to the outdoor environment as they viewed the classroom to be more important as opposed to the playground.

Furthermore, another study conducted by Lillian in (2010) on effect of play facilities on children's performance at pre-school activities showed that there is laxity of head teachers and teachers to engage children in play as it is considered a waste of time to them and a lot of emphasis is put on academics rather than learning through play. As a result less effort has been put by teachers to equip preschools with play facilities in E.C.E centers.

Moreover, a study conducted by Brockman (2011a), found that children's primary motive for engaging in physically active play was for social and enjoyment reasons, to prevent boredom and because they were aware of the physical and emotional benefits of being active. They also valued the freedom from adult control and the unstructured nature of physically active play. However, children felt that their active play was restricted by unattractive environment, fears and a lack of suitable play spaces. From these findings, Brockman, suggest that more encouragement should be given by schools to allow children outside at break times when it is raining, perhaps also providing them with waterproof clothing which mean that a piece of clothing made from material that does not let water through. Also believe that more safe places to play are required to reduce children's and parents' fears, which can prevent children from being active in their neighborhoods.

According to the American Academy of Pediatrics (2014) through rough and tumble play, children form social bonds, acquire different dominance ranks and learn what behaviors are acceptable, how to resolve conflicts and they learn right from wrong. Play is significantly related to creative problem-solving, co-operative behavior, logical thinking. Whilst playing together, children learn to co-operate, follow rules, develop self-esteem, control and learn generally how to get along with other people.

In Africa a study has been conducted on Teachers' use of play as a teaching strategy at pre-primary schools in Tanzania, findings showed that 57.5% of the teachers used play as a teaching strategy whereas 42.5% did not use play as a teaching strategy indicating that about half of the respondents did not use play as a teaching strategy. The study found out that teachers' level of motivation and availability of play materials emerged as factors which influenced teachers' use of play as a teaching strategy (Oncu & Uluer 2010). They also believed that play is one of the major activities that promotes children's imagination and creativity through which they can learn basic and social skills. However the researcher reveal that several research reports exist that show that most children were unable to exhibit creativity with play materials. They also found that most children were unable to use real objects for creative play. Their finding seem to be supported by the current practice of reducing play periods in early childhood education institutions and introducing in its place such activities as literacy, numeracy and computer skills development.

Additionally, a study done in Nigeria on teacher's perceptions and provisions on outdoor play for children revealed that outdoor play offers many benefits to children. According to this study, teachers believed that children who spent more time playing fall ill less often than others, who stay inactive. Further, the findings of this study found that 50 percent of sampled teachers perceive their roles during children's outdoors as supervising, coaching and instructing children on how to play (Okoruwa, 2017).

Furthermore, another research conducted by Miller & Almon (2009) shown that play is rapidly disappearing from kindergarten and early education as a whole. They believe that stifling play in early childhood education has dire consequences for both the children and the entire nation. This shift in emphasis is the practice in vogue in many "high-brow" early childhood education establishments in Nigeria, where terminal school achievement matters more than the school leaver's well-being.

A study on play point out that the playful nature of children makes play the most natural technique of teaching which would, if properly used by teachers, ensure smooth transition from home environment to school environment. To emphasize the need of play as a teaching method in early childhood, centers, the guide for early childhood advocate that young children are curious, active and learn, by doing. In early childhood children learn spontaneously through play. Minister of Education Guide (MoEG, 1984).

In Ethiopia, the major challenges confronting current pre-school education are lack of a standard curriculum, guidelines of age appropriate play materials, lack of access to early childhood education for almost all children and especially children from low socioeconomic backgrounds, lack of awareness about the value of play and type of care and education and misconception about children's learning (MoE, 2002).

Additionally, there is lack of age-appropriate stories/ culturally relevant story books that would be integrated with teaching. There is a tendency to believe that stories are necessarily narratives of the past generation and hence little efforts are seen fabricating those culturally, developmentally, and contextually relevant stories for instructional purposes. As a result, existing stories are overused, and only represent olden and rural life that bears little meaning to current developments. Stories and

picture books would have to reflect the Ethiopian multiethnic cultural values, morality (Habtamu, 1996).

Furthermore, Kindergartens' were faced materials and facility problems which include unavailability of text and supplementary (story) books for KG, Shortage of input materials like teaching aid materials, inadequate playing space and equipment (Tsegaye S. 2014).

According to MoE, (2003) report the government of Ethiopia recognized the importance of early childhood care and education (ECE) as a critical period that require due attention and a great deal of investments. With the intention of having intelligent and creative children, the government itself indirectly supports the initiatives for private kindergarten by preparing the curriculum as well as by training teachers. Nevertheless, kindergarten education is still one of the most neglected areas in Ethiopia.

1.2. Statement of the problem

In Bahir Dar City preschools have high populations such that the play equipment available is over stretched. As a result of this not all children in preschool are getting opportunity to engage in outdoor play with opportunity to manipulate a variety of play materials. As a result there has been poor engagement of children in outdoor play activities due to lack of play equipment.

As described above proper use of play material is important for children's all round development in the preschool. Because of play has been described as a vehicle for learning especially in early childhood. This implies that for effective learning, play must be incorporated in ECCE programs. Since teachers are key determinants of the experiences that children are exposed to, it is necessary to ascertain that they embrace use of play as a teaching strategy in pre-primary. Unfortunately, in Ethiopia, appropriate use of play materials in the preschools are neglected area. It is therefore important to carry out a research on the practice and challenges of utilization of play materials: In both faith based, government owned and private preschools in Bahir Dar City. Several researches have been conducted in other countries on different issues in different times. Among these; Mwalyego,(2014) conducted a research on the utilization of instructional materials at pre- primary schools in Tanzania, revealed that there was inadequacy of instructional materials in preprimary units, whereby the few available ones were mainly for teaching reading, writing and arithmetic. It was also revealed that the utilization of instructional materials was affected by teacher- pupil ratio, whereby the utilization was minimal in school with high teacher-pupil ratio. Also the classroom space and arrangement was poor such that effective facilitation by class teachers in using learning materials was restricted to only a few pupils.

Another study done by Tarimo (2013) in Tanzania about teachers' use of play as a teaching strategy at pre-primary schools, in the study, 57.5 percent had indicated that there are no enough play materials in their schools. This percentage implies that there are many schools in Tanzania that have significant shortage of outdoor play materials. The finding also showed that teachers' level of motivation and the availability of play materials emerged as hindering factors which influenced teachers' use of play as a teaching strategy.

Furthermore, a study conducted on effects of play equipment on preschool children's participation in outdoor play activities in Nairobi, revealed that children were engaged in outdoor play with inadequate play equipment and without the supervision of teachers. Recurrent repair and standby of broken out play equipment was also lacking (Elizabeth, 2013).

Moreover, a study conducted on play materials availability and utilization for development of gross motor skills at pre -primary school children in Nigeria, showed that eleven different play materials

were found in different quantities in the various establishments. Their utilizations also varied. The data revealed that three play materials such as balls, skipping ropes, and tiers were highly available in only three institutions. Five play items were moderately available at nine centers; while play materials availability was low at eight other centers. The daily utilization of the items was high for four play materials; moderate for another five and low for three play materials (Iroegbu, I. 2016).

Generally, the researchers Mwalyego, Tarimo, Elizabeth, and Iroegbu, (2016) studied on play materials availability and utilization for development of gross motor skills at pre -primary school children in Nigeria. Even though, the researcher conducted a research on play material availability and utilization for development of gross motor skills, he didn't look and assess the issues of practice and challenges of utilization of play materials. He only addressed play materials availability and utilization for development of gross motor skills; he has not examined play materials for social, physical, emotional, and cognitive developments. For that reason, the researcher is interested/ initiated to fill the gap through conducting a research on practice and challenges of utilization of play materials in government owned, faith based and private preschools of Bahir Dar City.

1.3. Objectives of the study

The general objective of this study was to assess the practice and challenges of utilization of play materials in both private, faiths based and government owned preschools of Bahir Dar City.

More specifically this study was attempted to address the following specific objectives

1. To identify the extent of availability of play materials for children learning in the selected preschool.
2. To examine to which teachers are properly using play materials as a teaching strategy in the elected preschool.
3. To find out the challenges that face in utilizing play materials.

1.4. Research Questions

The study was guided by the following leading questions

1. To what extent are plays materials are available in the classroom for children learning?
2. How teachers properly utilized the available play materials in the selected preschools?
3. What are the challenges in the utilization of play materials in the selected preschools?

1.5. Significance of the study

Play material make instruction real and spices the teaching and learning process. However, the use of play materials in the teaching and learning process in Ethiopian education system received little attention. The following stakeholders will be benefited from the study. These include curriculum developers, school administrators, classroom- teachers and future researcher.

The findings will be important to curriculum developers in evaluating and emphasizing the use of play materials by allocating more time for play in the timetable so that children can engage in quality and productive play. The school administrators will be able to get a better understanding on the value of play materials and hence provide more play materials for their preschools. The findings will also be important to classroom -teachers to attend in-service courses to learn more about play and material development for the benefit of the preschoolers.

Future researcher: The study can provide insight for other researchers to make further investigation on practice and challenges of utilization of play materials.

1.6. Delimitations of the study

Conceptually, the scope of the study was delimited on practice and challenges of utilization of play materials. In addition geographically, the study was delimited to government owned, private and faith based preschools in Bahir Dar City. These are Abune Gorgorios, Belay zelege and Eshet academy preschools which are found in Bahir Dar City specifically, Abunegorgoriosin kebele fifteen 100m near far distance from Blue Nile College and near to Iqra Academy, Belay zelege preschool found in kebele seven in front of papyrus hotel and Eshet academy which is found in kebele sixteen near to our guest house and in front of alpha mender academy.

1.7. Limitations of the Study

It is clear that research work cannot be free from constraints. For that matter, limitations were observed in this study, the most challenge that the researchers faced in the time of conducting this study was some respondents in some interview questions were not voluntary to give information regarding with the issues. Shortage of time to conduct the study was also a major constraint and lack of current local researches and reference materials even to compare results of the study. Despite the above problems, the researcher has exerted utmost effort and was able to overcome this problem by holding prolonged dialogue and discussion with the respondents.

1.8. Operational definition of terms

Play: -Any act of manipulation of objects or words by teachers and, or children for teaching or learning purpose respectively

Play materials: - are varieties of tools that teachers use in the teaching learning process

Practice: - use of play materials

Challenge:- any kind of problems that teachers face while using play materials

Faith based preschool: refers to faith based education program provided for children three to six years by religious organization

Pre-school:- Learning institution that provides basic educational foundation below the age of seven years.

Private preschool: - is an educational program which governed private and it is providing to teach preschool children

Governmental preschool: - is an educational program which governed by government and is focused on teaching preschool children.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHOD AND RESEARCH DESIGN

3.1. Introduction

This chapter deals with the research methodology of the study which includes, research methods, study design, description of the study area, target population, sample, sampling technique, methods of data collection instrument, research instruments, validity of the instruments, reliability of the instruments, methods of data analysis and ethical consideration.

3.2. Research method

This study employed qualitative research approach because it used to study problems or situations which are not studied well and to explore data in depth (Creswell, 2009). Qualitative approach is quite suitable to explore and understand the problems in detail in a natural setting (Creswell, 2007) and data are collected from multiple sources: Observing behaviors and interviewing participants. It is used to explore the issues in detail. Besides, O'Neil (2010) stated that qualitative research is used to explore and investigate detailed issues thoroughly. Qualitative approach is used when the study is inductive type, represent only the study area and the researcher considered that informants have different understanding to the problem being studied (Creswell, 2007, 2009; Vanderstoep and Johnston, 2009).

3.3. Research design

The major purpose of this study is to assess the practice and challenges of utilization of play materials in Bahir Dar City administration. To achieve this purpose the researcher employed exploratory research design to gain new insights, discover new ideas and/or increase knowledge of phenomenon. According to *Collins Co build English Dictionary for Advanced Learners* (2001:540), exploratory actions are done in order to discover something or to learn the truth about something." Burns and Grove (1998:38) define exploratory research as research conducted to gain new insights, discover new ideas and/or increase knowledge of a phenomenon. Therefore, the researcher employed this research design to explore the practice and challenges that encounter on teachers while using play materials and so as to clarify the practice and challenges of utilization of play materials in the study area.

3.4. Study site

The study was carried out in both faith based, private, and government owned preschools of Bahir Dar City. Bahir Dar City is located in the north western part of Ethiopia. Currently there are 83 preschools in Bahir Dar City. Out of these the researcher selects three preschools, one faith based, one government owned and one private preschool. From faith based Abune gorgorios, from government owned Belay zelege and from private Eshet academy are selected purposely for the following reason:-

- Due to voluntariness of the school for the research
- Due to no study has been done on this issue in the area.
- Due to the existence of relatively large number of preschools in Bahir Dar City

3.5. Data sources

Both primary and secondary data sources were equally significant to meet the intended objectives of this study. Thus, in this study, the researcher employed both primary and secondary sources in order to collect all the relevant data. Consequently, journal articles, PhD dissertations and MA thesis, and books were very important sources under the category of secondary sources of data. Data collected through interview, and direct observation used as primary sources of data. Therefore, as much as possible, the researcher tried to collect both primary and secondary data with regard to practice and challenges of utilization of play materials in AbuneGorgorios, Belay zelege and Eshet academy preschools in Bahir Dar City.

3.6. Participants

The participants of this study were KG teachers these who are teaching children in school, and principals of the preschools. In Bahir Dar City there are 48 preschools out of these 43 are private, and 5 are government owned preschools. There are 1488 children in the three preschools (665 are females

and 823 are males). And also there are 84 teachers in the three preschools including the assistant teachers, care givers and principals of the preschools out of these 82 are females and only two are males. Among these the researcher took the main teachers, and principals of the three preschools as study participants. Hence, the researcher selects Abune Gorgorios from faith based, Belay zeleke from government owned and Eshet academy from private preschools purposively. The sample sizes of this study were 15 teachers, and 3 principals of the preschools. The researcher purposively selected teachers of the preschools. This selected b/c purposive sampling technique is the conscious selection by the researcher of certain participants to include in the study, so the researcher select teachers these who have experiences in the use of play materials in the preschools by the helper of the principals and for principals compressive sampling technique was used because they are small in number.

3.7 Data Gathering Instruments

In the current study the researcher used two instruments, such as semi-structure interview, and direct observation. These instruments are considered important to triangulate the data and/or to combine the strengths of each instrument by minimizing their weaknesses.

3.7.1. Semi-Structured Interview

Semi structured interview b/c it helps the researcher to explore things that cannot directly observe, like feelings, thoughts and intentions. And it provides rich data (Wiersma, 2009).

Hence, in this study, semi-structured interview was conducted with teachers, and principals of the preschools. This instrument is particularly used to get data from preschool principals, and teachers since these bodies better understand the utilization of play materials. In doing this, interview guide questions were prepared with the main focus to get detail information focusing on the basic research questions. The reason behind the researcher is decided to use semi- structured interview because questions can be prepared ahead of time. This allows the interviewer to be prepared and appear competent during the interview. It also allows informants the freedom to express their views in their own terms.

3.7.2. Observation

According to Caswell (1982) observation is the most commonly used method of collecting data. Observations were conducted to get adequate data on basic research questions that focus on the availability of play materials. The researcher will have observation check lists to collect first-hand information to some research questions and to better facilitate the observation process. The observations of the school facilities are including: availability of play equipment used in outdoor and indoor activities, and their well utilization.

4. Trustworthiness of the Research

The credibility and dependability of the research were assured by the use of multiple methods. For instance, the researcher employed different data collection tools to cross-check the credibility of the data that were collected from the participants. This is for the purpose of what the social science researchers called data triangulation (Asnake, 2009). Moreover, throughout the study peer reviewers and advisor were contacted to minimize errors in conducting the research.

5. Methods of Data Collection Procedures

Before going to interview the participants the researcher took formal permission paper from the department of psychology? And would submit the letter to the selected preschools and would ask permission from the concerning body. The director of the school has been giving permission to the researcher. After the researcher gets permission from the director and I introduced myself to the

participants and then the researcher would give informed consent about the purpose of the interview and give direction about the interview.

6. Data Analysis

Thematic analysis

The researcher translated and transcribed the tape-recorded interviews, then read and reread the interviews in their entirety, reflecting on the interviews as a whole. Then, I summarized the interviews; keeping in mind that more than one theme might exist in a set of interviews. Once identified, the themes that appeared to be significant concepts linking substantial portions of the interviews were written down. In order to provide a brief description and understanding of the outcomes of the research in line with the research objectives. Data analysis in qualitative research consists of preparing and organizing of the data for analysis and then reducing the data into themes through the process of coding and condensing (Creswell, 2007). It is important to produce an insightful analysis that answers a particular research questions (Huberman & Miles, 1994). Consequently, the researcher employed thematic analysis to bring a clear answer for the established research questions.

According to Braun and Clarke (2006) thematic analysis is a method used for identifying, analyzing, and reporting patterns (themes) within the data. Thus, data that were collected from interviewees through semi-structured interview was structured into themes and patterns to have a clear analysis of the results based on the established objectives. The data were analyzed by using the data analysis stages of Huberman and Miles (1994) i.e. data reduction, data display and conclusion drawing and verification.

7. Ethical Consideration

The first ethical consideration is show respect for the participant's. And ask their permission before distributing the questionnaire to get their willingness. This study will be conducted on practice and challenges of utilization of play materials and all information from participants will be used only for research purpose. Therefore, the researcher will consider human dignity, right and assure that any information given by the respondents are kept confidential and secret.

CHAPTER FOUR

4.1. Results in interpretation

4.1.1 Results

The purpose of this study was to assess the practice and challenges of utilization of play materials in the selected preschool. In order to know the practice and challenges of utilization of play materials in both governments owned, faith based and private preschools, eighteen participants were interviewed. Out of those fifteen were preschool teachers and the three were principals in Bahir Dar City particularly in Abune gorgorios, Belay zelege and Eshet academy preschools. The researcher interpreted the idea of respondents and analyzed by own words.

4.1.2. Proportions of play materials and equipment with the number of student enrolled in the KG

As the checklist and interview result proved that the availability of outdoor equipment are too small due to the presence of high number of children enrolled in the KG with a few available play equipment, which is not enough proportional with the average of students. The researcher brought the finding, through considering both the regional and federal evaluation standard.

Table: 1. Availability of outdoor play equipment in Abune gorgorios preschool

No	Items	Student-material proportion of MoE	Student-material proportion of ANRSEB	Quantity of materials in school A	Student-material proportions of school A
	A, fixed play equipment				
1	Swings	2:40	1:30	2	2:49
2	Slides	2:40	1:30	2	2:49
3	Tunnels	2:40	1:30	1	1:49
4	Seesaw	2:40	1:30	1	1:49
5	Ladder	2:40	1:30	0	0:49
6	Merry go round	2:40	1:30	2	2:49
	B, Movable play equipment				
1	Balls	2:40	10:30	10	10:49
2	Tyres	10:40	10:30	0	0:49
3	Sand boxes	2:40	1:30	0	0:49
4	Skipping rope	-----	10:30	5	5:49

Here the researcher analyzed the data based on MoE and ANRSEB standard which was collected with the help of the observation checklist the data collected and analyzed was as shown below. In average there are 49 children in one class and the proportion of play equipment with children presented as follow 10: 49 balls, 2:49 swings, 1:49 seesaw, 2:49 slide, and 2:49 merry go round and 1:49 tunnels. Which mean that one ball for five children, one seesaw for forty nine children, one slide for five children, one merry go round for five children, and one tunnel for forty nine children. But minister of education recommends that, 10:40 balls, 2:40 tyres, 2:40 swings, 2:40 balance, 2:40 slide, 2:40 merry go round, 2:40 ladder, 2:40 tunnels, and 2:40 sand boxes. This means that one ball for four children, one tunnel for twenty children, one swing for twenty children, and one balance for twenty children, one slide for twenty children, one merry go round for twenty children, one ladder for twenty children and one tunnel for twenty children. In contrast with Amhara national regional state standard recommends that 10:30 balls, 10:30 tires, 10:30 skipping rope, 1:30 swing, 1:30 balance, 1:30 slide, 1:30 ladder, 1:30 tunnel, 1:30 merry go round, 1:30 sand boxes. This implies that this preschool not address the needs of children in outdoor play equipment.

Table: 2, Availability of outdoor play equipment in Belay zeleke preschool

No	Items	Student- material proportion of MoE	Student – material proportion of ANRSEB	Quantity of materials in school B	Student – material proportion of school B
	A, fixed play equipment				
1	Swings	2:40	1:30	2	2:41
4	Seesaw	2:40	1:30	2	2:41

5	Slide	2:40	1:30	2	2:41
6	Merry go round	2:40	1:30	2	2:41
7	Tunnels	2:40	1:30	0	0:41
9	Ladder	2:40	1:30	1	1:41
	B, Movable play equipment				
	Balls	10:40	10:30	6	6:41
	Tyres	10:40	10:30	0	0:41
	Sand boxes	2:40	1:30	0	0:41
10	Skipping rope	----	10:30	4	4:41

Unlikely, Abune gorgorios, in Belay zelege in average there are 41 children in one class and this preschool has a proportion of 6:41 balls, 2:41 swings, 2:41 seesaw, 2:41 slides 2:41 merry go round and 1:41 climbing frame respectively. However, minister of education recommends that, 10:40 balls, 10:40 tyres, 2:40 swings, 2:40 balances, 2:40 slide, 2:40 merry go round, 2:40 ladder, 2:40 tunnels and 2: 40 sand boxes respectively. Meanwhile, the ANRSEB recommends that, 10:30 balls, 10: 30 tyres, 10: 30 skipping rope 1:30 swings, 1:30 seesaw, 1:30 slide, 1:30 merry go round, 1:30 ladder, 1:30 tunnels and 1:30 sand boxes consequently. So this preschool is beyond that the standard of minister of education and Amhara national regional state bureau standard which mean that, in this preschool there are a great number of children in small number of play equipment, not only small but also they are not give service currently because they are old enough, broken and only two equipment are given service currently, but these play equipment are also age inappropriate. For further information the photo displayed the broken material that found in Belay zelege preschool as follow:

Table: 3 Availability of outdoor play equipment in Eshet academy

No	Items	Student –material proportion of MoE	Student –material proportion of ANRSEB	Quantity of playequipmnt in school E	Student material proportionschool E
	A, fixed play equipment				
1	Swing	2:40	1:30	2	2:49
2	Slide	2:40	1:30	2	2:49
3	Ladder	2:40	1:30	0	0:49
4	Seesaw	2:40	1:30	2	2:49
5	Merry go round	2:40	1:30	1:	1:49
6	Tunnels	2:40	1:30	0	0:49
7	B, Movable play equipment				
1	Balls	10:40	10:30	10	10:49
2	Tyres	10:40	10:30	0	0:49
3	Sand boxes	2:40	1:30	0	0:49
4	Skipping rope	-----	10:30	7	7:49

Likely Abune gorgorios in average there 49 children in Eshet academy and the proportion of play equipment with children are presented below as follow: 10:49 balls, 2:49 seesaw, 1:49 slide, 2:49 swings and 1:49 merry go round, 7:49 skipping rope respectively. But minister of education recommends that 2:40 balance, 2:40 slide, 2:40 merry go round and 2:40 ladder respectively. Additionally, amhara national regional state education bureau recommends that, 10:30 balls, 10:30 tyres, 10:30 skipping rope, 1:30 balance, 1:30 slide, 1:30 ladder, 1:30 tunnels, 1:30 merry go round, and 1:30 sand box respectively. This implies that high number of children with small play equipment and the opportunity of children playing in outdoor play are limited. The implication of this finding is that, the preschools are not providing sufficiently play equipment for the development of physical, social, cognitive and emotional development of the young children in the preschool. The data from this limited sample is an indication that the playthings for the development of physical, social, emotional and cognitive skills are not sufficient in the preschool to satisfy for the recreational needs of the preschoolers as well as for the developmental needs of children in the preschool. These findings, goes in line with (Ochanda, 2015) that carried out a study in Suba East, Migori County, to investigate the impact of play equipment on preschool children participation in outdoor play activities. She found that the most common play materials in her sampled preschools are balls, swings, slides, and merry round. The reasons why most schools have these types of equipment are that more preschoolers often prefer to use them compared to other kinds of play materials. It can be therefore deduced that these materials are cheap to install and may be used for various purposes. The current study findings were also goes in line with the report of (Tarimo, 2013) on use of play as a teaching strategy which revealed that most preschools lack enough play materials to engage children in meaningful play activities. Moreover, regarding with the adequacy of outdoor facilities the observation result confirmed that almost all the studied KGs had not similar physical settings and outdoor play equipment. The KG had not appropriate fence, well decorated wall with different and attractive pictures, numbers and letters. It is not far from the main road specially; Eshet academy and Belay zelege KG, and they had not wide and suitable play grounds. Which are free from harm full objects? In addition, these KGs had not suitable and adequate playground and sanitary facilities with near and at appropriate distance to the classroom. Moreover, though the numbers of the KGs children in all the three KGs were different, all KGs had not

similar indoor and outdoor play materials and equipment. More specifically, they had similar number of slides, swings, merry go round and balance. Each KG had not proportional number of outdoor materials and equipment to the number of children they have .For instance the number of children in average in Belay zelege, Abunegorgorios, and Eshet academy were, 41, 49and 49 respectively. However in the studied KG there were only one tunnel, in Abunegorgorios, one merry go round in Eshet academy. This was in contrary to what the MoE (2001) recommend that 2:40(one merry go round for forty children). This study result goes in line with Bruce (2011) who indicated that the bizarre assumption that knowledge acquired from indoors are superior to that gained from outside has created frequent lack of attention to the external environment and outdoor playing materials and equipment. This indicated that there was lack of outdoor playing equipment and materials in the studied KGs. This condition may affect the effective implementation of ECCE in general and the children’s holistic development in particular.

4.2 Maintenance of available outdoor play equipment

Regarding to maintenance of the available equipment materials were distributed to schools every year from government and NGO, but properly maintaining is the problem of in our school. Maintenance activities were not planned even if there is budget allocated school was not giving attention to maintaining materials (belay zelege preschool principal). Teachers of belay zelege preschool reported: In most cases materials are broken and piled in one room or in some place in the school compound every day but efforts are not made to maintain them.

5. Quantity of indoor available play materials

As the checklist result proved that the availability of indoor play materials are too minimal due to lack of good facilities of play materials in the preschool and lack of attention of teachers about the importance of learning corners for children’s holistic development.

Table: 5 Availabilityof indoor play materials in Abune gorgorios preschool

No	Items	Quantity of indoor available play material standard of ANRSEB	Quantity of indoor available play material in school A
1	Building blocks	4	0
2	Different toys	4	4
	family corner		0
	Cups	4	0
	Coffee pots	4	0
	Spoons	4	0
	Plates	4	0
	Small Toy beds	4	0
3	Medical corner		
	Aprons	4	0
	Syringes	4k	0
	Stethoscope	4	0
	Bandage	4	0
	Drug bottles	4	0
	Stretcher	4	0
4	shop corner		0
	Scale	4	0

As shown on the above table 5, this preschool has not sufficient indoor play materials for children to learn more in the classroom through manipulating and exploring different activities in the classroom. Instead there are different teaching aid materials that are posted on the wall that prepared from different materials like Model of letters, numbers, pictures, postures, alphabet letters, flash card, and story books. But the Amhara National Regional State Education office commends that, there be must be family corner under these four cups, four coffee pots, four spoons and four plates must be incorporated. But this school has not these play materials. In medical corner, four aprons, four syringes, four stethoscope, four bandages, four drug bottles, four stretcher must be there , in shop corner, four scale, there are many play materials mentioned in shop corner, but they are not quantify in number as a result the researcher left these play materials intentionally. So this preschool has not these play materials suggested by (ANRSEB, 2002) instead this preschool has different teaching aid materials these materials are presented as follow in photo;

But these posted teaching aid materials are not put in the specified place or they are not in the dimension of learning corners, just they are put in everywhere in the classroom. This implies that this, preschool has not their own learning corners. As we know there are different learning corners , such as Amharic learning corner, English learning corner, mathematics learning corner, Science learning corner and Geography learning corner and in each learning corner there are different materials that enhance children's all round developments. However, this preschool has no well-organized learning corners with insufficient play materials. Learning centers are the environmental skeleton of early childhood programs. They are designed to actively engage children in their own cognitive, language, physical, social, and emotional development. In a learning center—art, music, or dramatic play, for example—all children are invited to pursue their interests, learn to make meaningful choices, and build their skills. Equipment and materials are purposeful. Learning centers make the most sense, and are

most successful, when teachers understand the sequence of children’s play and learning (Texas Child Care, 2010). Of course, there are different pictures, postures models, flash cards and toys, but they are not sufficient rather they are samples for teaching and these materials are not seated in the specified learning corners as ANRSEB (2002) recommended each play materials must be founded in the specified learning corners so as to enhance children’s holistic development in the preschools.

Table: 6 Availability of indoor play materials in Belay zeleke preschool

No	Items	Quantity of available indoor play material standard of ANRSEB	Quantity of available indoor play materials in school B
1	Building blocks	4	0
2	Different toys	4	3
	family corner		0
	Cups	4	0
	Coffee pots	4	0
	Spoons	4	0
	Plates	4	0
	Small Toy beds	4	0
3	Medical corner		
	Aprons	4	0
	Syringes	4	0
	Stethoscope	4	0
	Bandage	4	0
	Drug bottles	4	0
	Stretcher	4	0
4	shop corner		
	Scale	4	0

The availability of different indoor materials is inadequate like school “A”.

This implies that, providing sufficient materials in well-organized learning corners are not given attention by the school teachers. So this indicated that there are no adequate indoor materials that can be for children’s holistic development.

Table: 7 Availability and adequacy of indoor play materials in Eshet academy

No	Items	Quantity of available indoor play material standard in ANRSEB	Quantity of available indoor play materials in school E
1	Building blocks	4	0
2	Different toys	4	2
	family corner		
	Cups	4	1
	Coffee pots	4	0
	Spoons	4	0
	Plates	4	0
	Small Toy beds	4	0
3	Medical corner		

	Aprons	4	0
	Syringes	4	0
	Stethoscope	4	0
	Bandage	4	0
	Drug bottles	4	0
	Stretcher	4	0
4	shop corner		
	Scale	4	0

Similarly, in belay zelege preschool, in Eshet academy there are no adequate indoor play materials that can be for learning coroners recommended by ANRSEB. Just instead of well-organized teaching aid materials there are different teaching aid materials that prepared from locally available resources, these teaching aid materials presented as follow:

According to procchner (1992:16) indoor materials and equipment are an integral part of the effective implementation of ECCE. These materials and equipment contribute their lion’s share in attracting and getting the attention of children for long period of time. It also makes the teaching learning process more concrete, suitable and easily understandable.

Adequacy and proportion of chairs, tables and shelves with the number of students per schools

As the observation checklist ascertained that, chairs, and tables are adequate with the number of students. However, this KG had not clean and well ventilated class-rooms with insufficient of light and full of attractive and different teaching aids.

Table: 8 regarding adequacy and proportion of chairs, tables and shelves in school A

No	Items	Adequacy of chairs, tables and shelves in ANRSEB	Student –chair, table, and shelve proportion of ANRSEB	Adequacy of chairs, tables &shelves in school A	Student- chair, table & shelve proportion in school A
1	Chairs	30	1:1	49	1:1
2	Tables	15	1:2	24	1:2
3	Shelves	3	1:10	2	1:24

Table: 9 regarding adequacy and proportion of chairs, tables and shelves in school “B”.

No	Items	Adequacy of chairs, tables and shelves in ANRSEB	Student –chair, table, and shelve proportion of ANRSEB	Adequacy of chairs, tables &shelves in school B	Student- chair, table & shelve proportion in school A
1	Chairs	30	1:1	49	1:1
2	Tables	15	1:2	8	1:5
3	Shelves	3	1:10	0	0:49

Table: 10 regarding adequacy and proportion of chairs, tables and shelves in school E

No	Items	Adequacy of chairs, tables and shelves in ANRSEB	Student –chair, table, and shelve proportion of ANRSEB	Adequacy of chairs, tables &shelves in school E	Student- chair, table & shelve proportion in school E
1	Chairs	30	1:1	49	1:1
2	Tables	15	1:2	24	1:2
3	Shelves	3	1:10	2	1:24

As the observation checklist result disclosed that all the studied KG had different proportions of child sized table, child sized chairs and child sized shelves. For instance in school “A” it has 1:2 child sized table, 1:1 child sized chairs and 1:24 child sized shelves. In school ” B”, 1:5 child sized table, 1:1 child sized chairs and 0:49 shelves at the last in school “E” it has 1:2 child sized table, 1:1 child sized chairs and 1:24 child sized shelves. Moreover, the observation result indicated that these GK had not clean and well ventilated class-room with insufficient amount of light and full attractive and different teaching aids. The result of this study contradict with Choudhury and Chudhury (2002) which explain that the presence of adequate indoor materials and equipment were fundamental for effective

implementation of various classroom activities in particular and in ECCE in general. More specifically, Bore and Picket (1954) suggested that every room used by KG should contain child sized furniture table and chairs that are work at puzzle, games and other that is necessary for children to develop new skills using real tools and real world. However, as the observation checklist revealed that the indoor materials and equipment which were found in one of the government owned KGs (Belay zeleke was quite different from the other KG. this KG had very narrow class size. It had also 1:5 child sized tables children ratio, 1:1 child sized chair and no child sized shelves in the class room. But there was a shelves outside the classroom in which the children put their meal and bags. Regarding to the negative impact of narrow class-rooms and absence of appropriate teaching aids, Bure(2011) stated that children cannot learn without real, direct and first hand experiences. Moreover, regarding the adequacy of indoor space, Gans Steindler and Almy (1952:352) noted that in schools where there is adequate space and shortage the varied activities go on without friction and all the materials can be tidied away and kept dust –free and orderly. On the other hand, where space is restricted, impromptu partnering of any kind occurs less often than when children circulate more freely in the block area. According to procchner(1992:16) indoor materials and equipment are an integral part of the effective implementation of ECCE. These materials and equipment contribute their lion’s share in attracting and getting the attention of children for long period of time. It also makes the teaching learning process more concrete, suitable and easily understandable. More particularly, locally produced mental maps and conceptual understandings (Chowdhury&Chowdhury(2002). Based on the observation result, it might be possible to deduce that teachers in the studied KG were producing different teaching aids, materials and equipment by using locally available resources and materials. Besides, though there was some inadequacy in child sized shelves, children were getting child sized chairs and tables in each studied KG.As a result children were getting good opportunity to sit and work at different puzzles, games and others that were necessary for children to develop new skills and facilitate the implementation of ECCE. Therefore, the studied government owned KGs had not similar indoor materials and equipment from that of private and faith based studied KG.

4.6.1 Safety of playground

Safety is a primary concern in all early care and education program. This is because young children, especially infants and toddlers, are just exploring their world and in the process they might hurt themselves unfortunately. Early childhood service providers can ensure safety for young children by creating a safe and supervised environment. By being saying this I would like to say something about the safety of playground that I had observed during my stay in the preschool. The safety of school “A” playground is hard and can lead to severe body injuries in case children had accidents during outdoor play. The playground of school “B” is grassy area, but the play equipment is broken, old enough, age inappropriate, poor repair. And the playground of school E is sandy area, even though they are cemented, grassy and sandy area of playground but the safety of these play materials aren’t well safe for children to play as they needed. This finding not goes in line with Childcare Service Act(2007).Play materials must be suitable to all children attending the outdoor activity that is they should take into consideration learners with special needs play materials used should offer children opportunity across several developmental areas thus being versatile and value for money not to forget the endless opportunities to play provided. Play materials should be those that are friendly, safe for the childcare setting as well as protect children from injury by ensuring furniture has no sharp edges and rough surfaces.

This broken equipment is presented in photo as follow:

This is contradict with the consumer product safety commission (CPS, 2010) recommends that young children's playground should be composed of age appropriate equipment scaled to their sizes, ability and developmental level for instance handles should be smaller, bridges and platforms should be low and have guard rails and hand rails, slides should be short (under 4 feet), and stairs should have gradual incline. A playground of this nature provides opportunity for children to engage in activities that satisfy their inquisitive nature and innate desire to discover and be creative.

As the interview result revealed that teachers use locally produced available teaching aid materials in each subject in the teaching-learning process.

4.8. Utilization of play materials

4.8.1 Utilization of teaching aid materials in the classroom

8.1.1 Curiosity of children to know type of color

As one of the participants said that, we use Amharic and English letters written by different colors to attract children's attention to enhance the capacity of children in their learning.

We have used them in a way that is appealing to the children, we cleaned up their environment, Make our seats comfortable. What aids in the class: What color: For example, if we write the numbers in the same color, they cannot be correctly identified. But one in green: Two in blue: Three in yellow: Four in red: In doing so, we write the children to be interesting because they even tell us that they have one green, two blue, three in yellow, and so they have the ability to understand. The second approach is that it is alphabetical, numerical formulation, this will determine our usage, and it is not good if we just cling to it as if we were just.

8.1.2. Locally produce teaching aid materials

Being the teaching aid materials locally produce it has so many advantages for children to learn and teachers to teach the student in easily manner. It is also culture oriented and being culture oriented children could easily know and understand the norms, and customs of the society. It is also inexpensive in terms of money and easily understandable in children. So locally produce teaching aid materials have a vital role for children holistic development.

As one of the study participant said that we use locally produce teaching aid materials this because locally produce teaching aid materials is culture oriented, less expensive interms of money and easily understandable. We benefit from having a sensitivity of what we do. For example, if I want to teach "N," I can teach with play, I can teach with song, I can teach by story so I can teach as many games as I can. For example, now I teach two kids in the middle of a room, and then they sing, and then they say, "I said, 'I am "N" I am "N" the simplest they understand. Then I will make them scratch with paper and they will learn by posting, they hear, they learn the letters. We say that the children love that toy, they will be happy, for example if they play chess now when they are learning or playing, so if you are tired of playing twice, then most people do not like it. I'll change another game if you like that a lot of them, then I understand that they are ready with the lesson or that the kids are ready for school because in that game I have a better idea. I use sound when I teach environmental science: the sound of a dog that is something they know from me. You see, they say hold the ban so they know the sheep. What do I say to a kid? No, the sheep will be slaughtered because I don't yell. For the most part, I use science in painting. To teach math, peas, nuts, and bay and use their own hand to count one to two, three to ten, and then I teach math in the way I say.

As one of the participant said that, we use the play area to interact with the children in a way that is interesting and attractive because the children, as they are able to maintain a good relationship with the children; to love the school, by using it. For example, nowadays in this game, we can always make the school a little more fun and more personalized. We repeat our instruction in the classroom and make it interesting and informative, for example, how is the shape after we have written the letter first, how often do you write it on a horizontal axis and then write it down after typing, then when it hits the handle it will fade. They know the shape of the alphabet and then identify her name. We use teaching aid materials in every subject. For example, if environmental science is a part of the human body, if the senses are the senses, gardening like a garden, if it is about fruits, we teach using fruits.

4.8.2 Fabric produces play materials and equipment

As the interview result revealed that many of fabric produced play materials and equipment not consider children's age appropriateness, not culture oriented this mean that not reflect the diverse cultures of the world rather it reflects the culture that the material producer's country and also not understandable or not clear for children to learn through manipulating and exploring their world using these materials, even not clear for teachers the one who didn't take KG training sohow to teach

children using these materials and equipment are Challengeable for the one who didn't take well training in ECCE and they are very expensive interms of money.

4.8.2. Utilization of play equipment in the outdoor

As the interview result disclosed that teachers used the outdoor play equipment in the way that attracts the attention of children, firstly they check the equipment at work and make them happy. Which mean that firstly they cleaned the play area to be free from any harm full objects and then order the children to play with their classmates with the help of their teachers and caregivers to keep children from injury.

As one of the participants said that outdoor play equipment, such as the swing one to this turn, one to that turn and not you to the cross and you play outdoor play equipment such as swing, slide, and balance rotation are used during these sessions. For example here is a K-1-K-3 now they play in different games when they are on vacation. Forty students are enough. Since they were children, we can now play, teach, and teach these children.

Therefore, the use of play materials in teaching learning process the studied KGs are at good practice except government owned KG. Teachers use the available teaching aid materials for the intended purpose to teach children in easily ways.

Teaching aids are an integral component in any class-room. It could help children in getting their attention, improving understanding, making easy to remember concepts and learning activities and enhancing academic achievement of children. Besides, children tend to remember what they have learned if the teaching learning process is supported by teaching aids (Chowdhury, and Choudhury 2002). Teaching aids have great value to make the lesson more concrete and interesting for children. According to the interview result with the KG teachers and principals and the observation result confirmed that in the entire studied private, faith based and government owned KGs there are different teaching aids which are produced by the teachers using locally available resources. However, as the result from the interview indicate that effective utilization of these teaching aids were much better in the private, and faith based preschools than the government owned KG. Even though there is lack of available play materials in these preschools, but teachers use the available materials in teaching learning process to teach children in easily way.

Challenges that had been observed in each preschools

As the interview result revealed that there are challenges that were existing in the current practices of play materials in the studied KGs: Lack of adequate outdoor and indoor play materials and equipment are the major challenges in studied KGs, lack of adequate playground space is the 2nd place being the major challenges in the selected preschools. Lack of standardized curriculum, Absence of properly trained KG caregivers (mogzit), lack of safe playground, lack of ECCE professionals are the 3rd major common problems observed in all preschools. Laziness amongst the teachers, lack of appropriate play materials specially in one of government owned KGs (Belayzeleke) lack of adequate learning corners, lack of separate feeding room, rest rooms.

5.1 An idea that raised by teachers and principals to solve the challenges that are observed in each preschools

If we were playing KG-1 today, because of what we do, then what would I do in the next game if you were sitting in a game where others were sitting and playing around with those kids?

The problem can be solved by having a spare time by playing with children. You can solve the

problem by making a rest room alone in order to solve safety problem make the playground attractive, rapid modification and adjustment so as to save the lives of the children, to solve the lack of play equipment play children in turn in program, to solve classroom problem /challenge make the classroom classified into five learning corners Amharic learning corners, English learning corners, science learning corners and geography learning corners to solve the problems of Ecce profession give proper training these who are not taking KG trading and hire took training in KG.

CHAPTER FIVE

Summary, Conclusions and Recommendations

This part of the study deals with the summary of major findings, the conclusions drawn, and the recommendations forwarded on the basis of the findings.

5.1. Summary of the Major Findings

This study investigated the practice and challenges of utilization of play materials in the three selected KG in Bahir Dar City. Three research objectives were formulated to guide the study. Objective one sought to identify the availability of play materials for children learning social, emotional, physical and cognitive development in the selected preschool. Secondly, to examine to which teachers are properly using play materials as a teaching strategy in the elected preschool? Thirdly, to find out the challenges that faces in utilizing play materials. The study employed exploratory design. The design was chosen because to gain new insights, discover new ideas on the availability of play materials, its utilization and challenges in the study area in detail. The study targeted 3 different preschools, and 15 teachers and 3 principals were interviewed. Purposive sampling technique was used for teachers and compressive sampling technique was used for principals'. Data was collected through checklist observation and interview. The data collected was analyzed through narration. Based on the analysis and interpretation of the data, it was possible to come up with the following major findings in relation to the basic research objectives:

Regarding the availability of indoor and outdoor play materials and equipment the studied KGs have inadequate availability of materials and equipment that can be for children holistic development in the preschools. The result of the study also revealed that the selected preprimary schools of Bahir Dar City seem to be in relatively good position in terms of efficient and effective play material utilization. Other play materials found in the indoor and outdoor were not adequately used to support the teaching learning process. Even though, teachers use the available teaching aid materials in teaching learning process, however, there are obstacles or challenges that hinder to use these materials. These challenges are lack of adequate play materials with absence of well-organized learning corners, lack of adequate playground and lack of feeding room are the some problems that face on teachers while using play materials in the teaching learning process in the studied KGs.

5.2. Conclusion:-

In accordance with the study results, it can be concluded that, if the studied preschools do not meet the playground, and adequate indoor learning corners indicated by ANRSEB, then the holistic development of children will be impeded.

References

1. Amhara National Regional State Education Bureau (2002) *preprimary education program's standard. Bahir Dar, Ethiopia*

2. American Academy of Pediatrics (2014). *The social emotional development of young children. Psychology today. The need for pretend play in child development.* New York: Public Health. Among Young schools age Children in Tanzania. PhD. dissertation: Albert
3. Best, J.W. & Kahn, J.V. (2003). *Research in education.* Boston: Library of congress cataloguing- in publication data.
4. Brady, L M, Gibb, J, Henshall, A & Lewis, J (2008) *Play and Exercise in Early Years: Physically active play in early childhood provision.* London: NCB. Available online at: <http://www.culture.gov.uk/images/research/Playresearch2008.pdf> (Accessed Nov. 2011).
5. Brockman, R, Jago, R & Fox, KR (2011a) 'Children's active play: self-reported motivators, barriers and facilitators', BMC Public Health, 11, 7. Available online at: <http://www.biomedcentral.com/1471-2458/11/461> (Accessed November 2011).
6. Brown, W. (2009). Social and environmental factors associated with preschoolers' no sedentary physical activity. *Child Development*, 80, 45-58.
7. Bruce, T. 2011. *Early Childhood Education (4th ed.)*. Oxon: Hodder Education.
8. Caswell, F (1982). *Success in statistics, Hong Kong*: Wing King Tong Ltd.
9. CelebiOncu, E. & Ozbay, E. (2005). *ErkenCocuklukDonemindekiCocuklarIcinOyun, KokYayincilik*, Ankara
10. Chowdhury, A. and Choudhury, R. 2002. *Pre-school Children: Development, Care and Education*. New Delhi: New Age International Publisher
11. Creswell, J. W., & Plano Clark, V. L. (2011). *Designing and conducting mixed methods research (2nd ed.)*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications, Inc.
12. Daniel, G. (2010). *The Practice and Problems of Early Childhood Education: the case of Yekati-12 Kindergarten*. Unpublished BA Thesis of the AAU.
13. Davies, M. (1997). The Teacher's Role in Outdoor Play: Preschool Teachers' Beliefs and Practices. *Journal of Australian Research in Early Childhood Education*, 2-3.
14. Dodge, D (2002) *Creative curriculum for preschool (4thed)* Washington, DC: teaching strategies.
15. Elis, M.J. & H. Arnold, (2006). *The educator's guide to emotional intelligence and academic achievement: Social-emotional learning in the classroom.* Thousand Oaks. CA: Corwin Press.
16. Elizabeth, A. (2013). *Effects of play equipment on preschool children's participation in outdoor play activities in Suba east division, Migori County.* (MA Thesis, University of Nairobi).
17. Essay, UK. (2018). *Learning through play: School development.*
18. Froebel, F. (1885). *The education of man.* New York: A Lovell and Co.
19. Gans, R, Stendier, C. and Almy, M. (1952). *Teaching Young Children.* New York: World Company.
20. Gichuba, Opatsa and Nguchu (2009) *General Methods of Teaching Young Children and Materials Development.* Nairobi: Longman Publishers.
21. Gill, T. (2007), no fear. *Growing up in a risk averse society*, London: Calouste Gulbenkian foundation.

22. Iroegbu, I. (2016). Play materials availability and utilization for development of gross motor skills in Nigeria. (World Journal of Social Science, 3, No. 2; 2016 Awolowo University).
23. Jack, L. N., & Christopher, H. H. (2013). Playground Characteristics to Encourage Children to Visit and Play. *Journal of Physical Activity and Health*, 10, 1201-1208.
24. Jotia, A. L. (2006). *The Quest for Deep Democratic Participation: Schools as Democratic Spaces in the Post-Colonial Botswana*. Retrieved from http://etd.ohiolink.edu/sendpdf.cgi/Jotia%20Agreement%20Lathi.pdf?ohiou11473_60469 on 28 March 2009.
25. Kamen, T (2005), *The play workers handbook* London: Hodder Education
26. Kaplan, (2019). Early learning company.
27. Kenya Institute of Education (1999). *Guide lines for ECD of Kenya*. Nairobi: NACECE.
28. Kenya Institute of Education (2003). *A guide for early childhood development in Kenya*. KIE Nairobi: NACECE.
29. Kerich, M., & Okioma, L. M. (2015, July-Aug). Suitability of Children's Outdoor Play Environment in City ECD Centers for their Cognitive Development. *IOSR Journal of Research & Method in Education (IOSR-JRME)*, 5(4), 57-61.
30. KIE (2008). *Handbook for Early Childhood Syllabus*. Nairobi: KIEV
31. Kiruki, J. N (2011). *The Impact of Instructional Resources on Children's Learning Achievements in Selected Pre-Schools in Nairobi North District, Nairobi Province in Kenya*. (Masters Dissertation): UoN Library Archives.
32. Lester, S and Russell, W (2010) *Children's right to play: An examination of the importance of play in the lives of children worldwide*. Working Paper No. 57, The Hague, and The Netherland: Bernard van Leer Foundation.
33. Lillian, K. (2010). Effect of play on children's performance in preschool activities. Suba east, Migori District. Unpublished Diploma of Education in Early Childhood Education Research project, Dona hill College
34. Lindon, J (2007) *Understanding Children and Young People: Development from 5–18 years*. London: Hodder Arnold.
35. Lockheed, Marriaine, E and verspoor, A, (1991). *Improving primary Education in Developing countries*, New, York, and Oxford University press for the world Bank.
36. Malone, K. & Tranter, P. (2003). *Children's Environmental learning and the use design and management of play grounds*.
37. Marjanovic-Umek, L and Lesnik-Musek, P (2001) 'Symbolic Play: Opportunities for cognitive and language development in preschool settings', *Early Years*, 21, 1, 55–64
38. Marshall, C. and Rossman, G. B. (1999) *Designing Qualitative Research*, (3rd edn). Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE.
39. Miller, E., & Almon, J. (2009). *Crisis in the kindergarten: Why children need to play in school*. Maryland: Alliance for childhood.

40. Millicent, A. (2009). Impact of learning materials on children's performance in ECE centers Suba East, Migori District. Unpublished Diploma of Education in Early Childhood Education Research Project, Asumbi College.
41. Mincemonger, C., & Horning L. C. (2006). 101+ Ways to keep Kids Busy: Better Kids. Retrieved from: Extension.psu.edu/Publication/ua229
42. Mugenda M.O. & Mugenda A. (2003); *Research methods: Qualitative and quantitative Approaches*, Africa Center for technology studies, Nairobi, Kenya
43. Mwalyego, S. (2014). An investigation on the utilization of instructional materials in morogoro municipality. (PhD Dissertation, University of Tanzania).
44. Mwaura, K. (1998). Research on play learning materials on the development of cardinal numbers and other learning areas in children. Kiambu District- Unpublished masters of education in early childhood Research project, Kenyatta University.
45. National Centre for Early Childhood Education (2004). *Preschool teachers' Guide Toys materials for play and Learning*: Nairobi, KIE.
46. Obiagwu, R.B. (2012). Exploiting toys to achieve optimum performance in Early Childhood Education, Paper presented at the 4th international conference organized by Early Childhood Association of Nigeria (ECAN) and institute of Education, O.A. U. Ile-Ife, Nigeria.
47. Oncu, E. C., & Uluer, E. (2010). *Preschool children's using of play materials creatively*. *Procedia: Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 2(2), 4457-4466. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2010.03.711>
48. Parten, M. (1932). Social participation among preschool children. *Journal of Abnormal and Social Psychology*, 27, 243-269.
49. Pilot, D.F., & Hungler, B.P. (1999). *Nursing research principles and methods*. Philadelphia: JB Lippincott Company.
50. Polit, D. & Beck, C.T. (2004). *Nursing research: principles and methods*. 7th Edition. Philadelphia: Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.
51. Prochner, L. 1992. Themes in the Late 20th Century Child Care and early Education: A Cross National Analysis. In: G.A. Woodil, J. Barnhard, and I. Pronchner (Eds.). *International Handbook of Early Childhood Education*. London: Garland Publishing.
52. Tarimo J. (2013). Teachers' use of play as a teaching strategy at pre-primary schools in Mwanga district, Kilimanjaro region, Tanzania. (MA Thesis, Kenyatta University).
53. Tassoni, P., K. Beith, K. Bulman, & H. Eldridge, (2007) *Child Care and Education: Cache Level 3*, 4th edition, Oxford: Heinemann.
54. Universal Basic Education Commission (UBE 2013). *Training Manual for Early Childhood Care Development and Education (ECCDE)*: Abuja, Universal Basic Education Commission. University Press.
55. Vig, S. (2007). *Young Children's Object Play: A Window on Development*. *Journal of Developmental Psychological Disorders*, 19, 201-215
56. Waithaka, E.N. (2009). Basics of in-doors and outdoor play activities for young children, Kenyatta University, Unpublished module.
57. Wiersma, W., & Jurs, S. (2009). *Research methods in education: An introduction*. MA: Pearson.